

ISic0670

I.Sicily inscription 0670

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

limestone

Object

base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Michael Economou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance

Excavation of foundations of Municipio

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Messina, Museo regionale interdisciplinare di Messina, inventory A238

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Cerrinae ·
2. L(uci) · f(iliae) · Cottiae
3. Cottia · Euphrosyne
4. filiae piissimae
5. s(ua) · p(ecunia) · p(osuit) · l(oco) · d(ato) · d(ecreto) · d(ecurionum) ·
6. [etob] dedicationem earum
7. [den]arios · divisit

Apparatus

Text of Bitto 2001

Translation (en)

Cottia Euphrosyne set this (statue) up out of her own money for Cerrinia Cottia, daughter of Lucius, a very dutiful daughter, in the place determined by the decuriones. She distributed denarii in return for the dedication of these (statues).

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175739

EDR 081482

EDCS 6100247

PHI 313668

Bibliography

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Manganaro, G. 1989. Iscrizioni Latine nuove e vecchie della Sicilia. *Epigraphica.* 51: 161-196. At 162 no.1 fig.1

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